

Determinants of Television and Film Viewing Culture among Families in the Digital Era: A Perceptual Study in Nigeria

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Abstract

The re-emergence of shared television and film viewing culture has become a socio-scholastic discourse. This study contributes to this emerging discourse by examining the frequency and duration of family viewing in the digital era, as well as identify socio-demographic determinants, and household-level determinants of family viewing. This study was hinged on the family systems theory. The research conceptualised TFVC as a subsystem that supports family cohesion and intergenerational interaction. A descriptive survey design was employed. Four hundred (400) Nigerian adults aged 17 to 67 were sample for the study using purposive and snowball sampling techniques. Data were collected via an online questionnaire, which demonstrated acceptable reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.78$). Findings revealed that most families engaged in one to two hours of shared viewing per session, with 27.6% watching daily and 31.6% rarely co-viewing. Education emerged as the strongest socio-demographic predictor, with tertiary-level ($B = 0.718$, $p = .001$) and postgraduate education ($B = 0.533$, $p = .012$) positively associated with TFVC. Household access to mobile phones significantly predicted higher TFVC ($B = 0.688$, $p = .002$), while family size and role were not significant. When socio-demographic and household-level factors were combined, device availability remained the strongest positive predictor, even as age and work hours negatively influenced TFVC. The study concludes that television and digital media remain vital for family cohesion and communication in the digital era, with education and access to devices as key determinants of shared viewing. The study recommends establishing consistent co-viewing routines, which should involve all household members regardless of educational background, and ensuring adequate access to multiple viewing devices to facilitate flexible and engaging family media experiences.

Keywords: Digital era, co-viewing, family communication, television viewing culture, perceptual study

Introduction

Before the advent of the digital era, families use to watch TV together on a regular basis. This was a very crucial aspect of family life. In many homes in Nigeria back in the day, this was the only opportunity for families to interact as well as deliberate values and norms. Shared television and movie viewing time as a family still ranks as one of the most cherished nostalgic moments growing up (Nawer, 2023). At a moment, TV went from ‘one screen’ to ‘many screens’; it started with the addition of computer screens, and now there is a saturation of mobile phone and iPad screens everywhere (Adeleke, 2016). This availability of more devices impacted negatively on family time. Adeleke opines that with just one TV set at home, family often had more time together especially in the evenings. Television watching time, which use to be a focal point in a lot of homes for many years, is falling out of favour amongst most youngsters. It is becoming less likely that families will meet round the television today as it was yesteryears. While parents seem not particularly surprising with their children retreating into their own digital worlds, this is not about the children but much more about how the shape of family life and interaction is changing. Television, as a shared place for families to interact and share values, is being pushed back into the corner (Coughlan, 2018).

With the proliferation of the digital media, there are other options to pick over shared television time with family such as playing video games or watching favourite movie or YouTube video individually. The modern world is changing everything at a great speed. People are busy and can rarely match their free time with everyone else free time in the family in order to watch TV together. (Nawer, 2023). TV viewing habits are changing drastically. This started initially as a result innovation of new technology and evolving platforms. Most recently, the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic added a shift to the culture (Fatemi, 2022). Watching TV, which use to merely refer to “sitting on the couch in front of a television set”, has significantly metamorphosed. First, it shifted to individualistic screen-watching time. With the advent of mobile phones and various streaming platforms such as Netflix and YouTube, people preferred to select and watch, even binge-watch, contents that were with their scale of preference (Fangel, 2024). This was a relief from the struggles of movie or programme selection during shared viewing time with family. According to Fatemi (2022), where and how people watch shows has changed from TV-style appointment viewing to streaming, especially among youngster. Streaming services recorded over 50% of viewers under 35; viewers ages 60 and up said they spend only 14% of their entertainment time with streaming services, but those ages 15–29 said they spend 22% of the time streaming.

The next change in the nature of television and screen viewing time changed with the outbreak of the pandemic. When the pandemic hit, parents began spending more time with their kids at home again. They prioritised family-focused activities, and more often than not, that meant watching TV. The year 2022 had the highest level of co-viewing in the awards’ history: more than half of kids watched with an adult, a triple-digit increase over the previous year. The COVID-19 effect on family television watching time. Co-viewing increased the effectiveness of ads; watching together, both kids and adults were more attentive. The argument that that actual television sets still have the biggest impact or, alternately, “that the living room couch is still the most important place for advertisers to reach kids and families”, sprang up again (Fatemi, 2022, para. 5). Fangel (2024) corroborates that co-viewing on connect TV which seemed to have been lot in the trend of things is on the rise once more. A research, conducted this year by Google in partnership with Ipsos, highlighted that despite the rise of fragmented viewing across devices, viewers are still

yearning shared experience and connected TVs are a conduit for bringing people together more than ever before.

Through connected TV, shared TV watching time as emerged again on the table of socio-scholastic deliberations. Necessity demands that this discourse begins from the point of socio-cultural importance. Television is re-stamping its relevance as a powerful medium that often brings families together (Gillin, 2019). McGraw(2024) opines that streaming TV has ushered in a new era of convenience, diversity, and personalised viewing experiences, which impacts on family dynamics, cultural connections, and marketing opportunities for advertisers. Although the digital media reduced family time as the younger generation becomes more individualistic and attached to their phones, shared television and movie times are re-emerging as meaningful opportunities for shared experiences. These shared moments can strengthen interactions, deepen connections, and foster healthier family bonds. A functional family, in turn, produces responsible and functional members of society who contribute to security, sustainability, and development. Conversely, a dysfunctional family tends to produce individuals who negatively affect society, leading to higher crime rates, reduced collective well-being, and hindered social progress. Since the acculturation and socialisation process of youngsters is significantly influenced by the television and film viewing culture at home, then, it is essential to pay critical attention to it (Baji, 2020).

As the discussion of the relevance of shared television and film time is resurfacing, there is a need to revisit the factors that determine these television and film viewing culture within families. It is as a result of this that this study examines that determinants of television and film viewing culture. This is to ascertain the extent to which socio-demographic determinants and household-level determinants can individually as well as jointly predict television and film co-viewing culture among families in Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of this study are to:

- i. examine the frequency and duration of television and film viewing culture among family in the digital era;
- ii. identify the socio-demographic determinants of television and film viewing culture among family in the digital era; and,
- iii. ascertain the household-level determinants of television and film viewing culture among family in the digital era.

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the execution of this study:

- H₀₁: Socio-demographic characteristics do not significantly predict family television viewing culture.
- H₀₂: Household-level determinants do not significantly influence family television viewing culture.
- H₀₃: Both socio-demographic and household-level determinants does not significantly predict family television and film viewing culture.

Literature Review

Media including television and films are integrated in the daily life of every family and are part of family rituals and traditions. Their uses have the potential to enhance family relations and facilitate interactions and cohesion within the family (Coyne, Padilla-Walker, Fraser, Fellow, & Day, 2014, Courtois & Nelissen, 2018). Following this, the family systems theory developed by Murray Bown places media as an instrument of interaction with the complex cycle of the family life (Broderick,

1993 in Courtois and Nelissen, 2018). Consistent with the positive link between family rituals and family closeness, several studies have shown that media, especially television and films, are often used by families to elicit family functioning (Coyne et al., 2014), family harmony, and family connection (Padilla-Walker, Coyne, & Fraser, 2012). However, family television viewing can also account for decreased family communication /and conflict, such as conflicts about volume that children watch or about the programs that are being watched in general (Courtois & Nelissen, 2018).

Series of studies has been conducted to reintroduce the discussion of television and film viewing culture (TVC) among families in the digital era. According to Courtois and Nelissen (2018) despite the robust prevalence of family viewing, alternative social patterns coincided with the appropriation of screen technologies beyond living room television. These deviations from family viewing are associated with lower closeness of family members between generations. However, younger generations who co-watch television and film together reported higher levels of closeness with their generational counterparts. Iheanacho et al. (2020) found that while television viewership is high among families in Uyo, channels such as Zee World were rarely considered a shared family activity. This reveals a selective nature of co-viewing in contemporary households. With the individualisation of leisure time activities, according to Kraus, Stašová, and Junová (2020), co-watching and shared television time has been moderately reduced on one hand. Nevertheless, the multiplicity and mobility of media at home positively predicts co-viewing television time in families. Eighty-four percentage of Europeans watch television every day or almost every day; mostly with the television set or on the Internet; with the proportion of people watching it on the Internet has been rising continuously. Even amongst children, Bassul, Corish and Kearney (2021) confirms that, in Ireland, parents' sociodemographic behaviours are associated with children's TV screen time. Within the different sedentary behaviours evaluated, parents' TV viewing was positively associated with children's TV screen time.

These new ICTs, especially mobile social media, according to Hänninen, Taipale and Korhonen (2021), enhance solidarity among family members who do not live in the same household. This includes democratisation of the family, rise of proxy persons, intensification, and compartmentalisation of family communication on family solidarity. Olimma (2023) corroborates that availability of mobile apps has led to the on-demand shift in TVC. Mobile phones and tablets are used as a second screen among the youngest viewers. Almost 40% of households with children under seven had one or two tablets for viewing television programmes and other broadcast contents. Grant (2024) ascertained that co-viewed television time improves social interaction and closeness to the family member that co-viewing is done with the most. Mothers being the most co-viewing family member. In addition, Inobemhe, Ja'afaru and Ekhareafu (2025) revealed that digital media and associated technologies also played a significant role in the changing narratives of family TV content viewing from shared experience to individual viewing. This is due to emerging alternative social patterns that favour handheld and pocket-sized screen technologies other than those in the living room.

Methodology

This study was conducted using a descriptive survey research method. The population of this study consisted of adult Nigerians between the ages of 17 and 67. Using statistics from the National Population Commission, as of mid-2025, the estimated population of Nigeria for the age bracket of 17 to 67 years is approximately 126.7 million people. The sample size for this study was

approximately 400 participants determined using the Tayo Yaro formula. To obtain participants, a combination of purposive and snowball sampling techniques was employed. Purposive sampling was used to target adults who were active users of digital communication platforms, as the survey was administered online. Snowball sampling was incorporated to increase reach by encouraging participants to share the survey within their social networks.

The instrument for data collection in this study was a meticulously structured questionnaire, crafted to gather comprehensive information relevant to the research objectives. The internal consistency of the instrument was tested using Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficient. Eight items selected from the questionnaire that measured shared family TV/movie viewing and its impact on family cohesion showed acceptable internal consistency (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.78$) (Table 1). This indicates that the items reliably measure the same underlying construct. Corrected item-total correlations ranged from 0.44 to 0.65, demonstrating that all items contributed positively to the scale. This confirms that the scale is suitable for use in further statistical analyses, including regression models and moderation testing.

Table 1: Reliability Test using Cronbach Alpha

Items	M	SD	Corrected Item-Total r
DiscussionImmediatelyAfterWatching	3.20	0.95	0.55
ImprovedConversations	3.10	1.00	0.62
FamilyConnectionAfterWatching	3.25	1.07	0.49
HelpResolveConflict	3.15	1.12	0.44
ViewingStrenghtensRelationship	3.30	1.05	0.60
FeelingOfClosenessAfterWatching	3.25	1.08	0.58
CreatesSenseOfUnity	3.28	1.03	0.65
PositivelyImpactHappiness	3.35	1.00	0.57

Note. Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.78$ (95% CI [0.74, 0.82]); standardised $\alpha = 0.79$; mean inter-item correlation = 0.53. Response scale ranged from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree).

Data collection was conducted through an online questionnaire designed using Google Forms. The survey link was distributed through multiple digital channels, including direct personal messages, broadcast messages, WhatsApp communities, and WhatsApp status posts. Friends and colleagues were also requested to reshare the survey link to extend coverage and enhance participation. This method ensured that the questionnaire reached a wide and diverse pool of respondents across Nigeria. Data collection lasted for 23 days, during which the number of completed responses reached the required sample size.

Data analysis was conducted using RStudio (version 2025.09.2+418). The online survey dataset was imported from Excel, and numeric codes were converted into descriptive labels for clarity. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations was used to summarise respondents’ demographic characteristics and family TV/movie viewing patterns. Likert-scale items measuring Television and Movie Culture (TVC) were converted to numeric scores (1–5), and a composite TVC score was calculated for each participant. Multiple linear regression analyses were used to test the hypotheses formulated for this study. The joint effects of the independent variables was tested with standardised beta coefficients to compare relative predictor strength.

Analysis and Results

Descriptive statistics were computed for both continuous and categorical variables to provide an overview of participants’ characteristics and family viewing patterns. The average age of the study’s participants was 34.48 years (SD = 11.25), with the younger participant at 17 years and the older at 67 years. On average, participants worked approximately 8 hours daily (SD = 3.00), within a range of 0 to 20 daily working hours. The average size of families represented in this study was about 5 members (SD = 1.89), with nine (9) as the highest number in a family. Families had an average of three devices through which they could watch television and/or movies (SD = 1.46), where 1 was the minimum and 5 was the maximum. See Table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Continuous Variables

Variable	M	SD	Median	Min	Max	Range	Skew	Kurtosis
Age (years)	34.48	11.25	32	17	67	50	0.71	-0.03
Work Hours (daily)	7.77	3.00	8	0	20	20	0.61	2.62
Family Size	5.33	1.89	5	1	9	8	0.15	-0.82
Viewing Devices (count)	2.90	1.46	3	1	5	4	-0.16	-1.48
Platforms (count)	1.64	0.96	1	1	5	4	1.72	2.80

Source: Online Survey, 2025

Families used approximately two (M = 1.64) on an average out of five platforms listed as viewing avenues. The average age of the participants showing a midlevel between younger adults and older adults. Age (skew = 0.71, kurtosis = -0.03) and work hours (skew = 0.61, kurtosis = 2.62) were positively skewed but to a little extent, while family size (skew = 0.15, kurtosis = -0.82). Viewing devices (skew = -0.16, kurtosis = -1.48) were approximately normally distributed. The number of platforms used was positively skewed (skew = 1.72, kurtosis = 2.80). This highlights that most families used fewer platforms, however, a little proportion used multiple platforms. These results suggest moderate variation in socio-demographic and household determinants of television and film viewing culture. It, therefore, provides strong basis for additional analysis. See Table 3 below.

Table 3: Primary Platforms and Viewing Devices Used by Participants

Category	Subcategory / Count	Freq.	%
Primary Platform	Netflix	116	29.6
	Local TV channels	112	28.6
	YouTube	76	19.4
	I don’t watch TV or movies with my family	36	9.2
	Other	36	9.2
	DVDs/Blu-ray	16	4.1
Number of Platforms Used	1	232	59.2
	2	100	25.5
	3	40	10.2
	4	8	2.0
	5	12	3.1
Primary Viewing Device	TV	292	74.5
	DSTV/GOTV/StarTimes/Strong or the likes	68	17.3

	Mobile Phones	20	5.1
	Laptop	12	3.1
Number of Devices Used	1	116	29.6
	2	40	10.2
	3	52	13.3
	4	136	34.7
	5	48	12.2

Source: Online Survey, 2025

Families primarily relied on television as their main viewing device, with 74.5% of participants reporting its use, and Netflix as the most popular platform, used by 29.6% of families. On average, households used approximately two platforms (M = 1.64) out of the five listed, with most families (59.2%) relying on a single platform, while fewer used two (25.5%), three (10.2%), four (2.0%) or all five platforms (3.1%), indicating a positively skewed distribution (skew = 1.72, kurtosis = 2.80). The number of viewing devices varied, though the distribution was approximately normal (skew = -0.16, kurtosis = -1.48), suggesting that while television was dominant, some families used multiple devices for shared viewing. Television and Netflix are the primary avenues for family viewing, with moderate variation in platform and device use across households (Table 3). Slightly more than half of the participants for this study were female (54.1%), while 45.9% were male (as seen in Table 4 below). Regarding education, most participants held postgraduate degrees (56.1%), followed by tertiary education (42.3%). Family roles were balanced between fathers and mothers (29.6%), with 40.8% identifying as children.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Categorical Variables

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	180	45.9
	Female	212	54.1
Education	Primary	3	0.8
	Secondary	3	0.8
	Tertiary	166	42.3
	Postgraduate	220	56.1
Family Role	Father	116	29.6
	Mother	116	29.6
	Child	160	40.8
Frequency of Shared Viewing	I don't watch	36	9.2
	Rarely	124	31.6
	Weekly	44	11.2
	2-3 times a week	80	20.4
	Daily	108	27.6
Duration of Shared Viewing	I don't watch	48	12.2
	< 30 minutes	32	8.2
	30 min – 1 hr	80	20.4
	1-2 hours	128	32.7
	2-3 hours	48	12.2
	> 3 hours	56	14.3

Initiator of Shared Viewing	I don't watch	32	8.2
	Myself	72	18.4
	Spouse	88	22.4
	Parents	12	3.1
	Children	68	17.3
	Siblings	28	7.1
	Anyone with a good movie/series	92	23.5

Source: Online Survey, 2025

In terms of shared television or movie viewing culture, as captured in Table 4 above, most of the participants (31.6%) rarely watched TV with their families. Families that watched TV/movies together daily, made of 27.6%, this was followed by those who watched 2–3 times a week (20.4%). A majority of the families spend 1–2 hours together (32.7%), followed by those who watched 30 minutes to 1 hour (20.4%). When considering who usually initiated shared viewing, 23.5% reported that anyone with a good movie or TV series initiated it, 22.4% indicated the spouse, 18.4% the respondent themselves, 17.3% children, 7.1% siblings, 3.1% parents, and 8.2% did not engage in shared viewing. Overall, these results demonstrate variability in family viewing habits, roles, and participation, providing a comprehensive overview of television and movie viewing culture among Nigerian households.

Table 5. Regression of Socio-Demographic Determinants on Television and film viewing culture among Families in Nigeria

Predictor	B	SE	t	p
(Intercept)	3.009	0.294	10.24	< .001
Gender (Female)	-0.124	0.083	-1.49	.136
Age	0.0035	0.0034	1.04	.300
Education Level (Tertiary)	0.718	0.221	3.25	.001
Education Level (Postgraduate)	0.533	0.210	2.54	.012
Work Hours	0.011	0.011	0.97	.331

Model Fit: $F(5, 387) = 3.64, p = .003, R^2 = .045, Adjusted R^2 = .033$

The regression model in table 5 that ascertained that socio-demographic determinants such as gender (female), age, tertiary education levels (undergraduate and post graduate) were statistically significant predictors of family television and film viewing culture (TVC), $F(5, 387) = 3.64, p = .003$, explaining 4.5% of the variance in TVC ($R^2 = .045$). The level of education of family members significantly predicted TVC. Families with a member having tertiary education such as undergraduates reported the highest the beta score for TVC ($B = 0.718, SE = 0.221, t = 3.25, p = .001$); which was followed by families with members who are postgraduate students with a higher TVC too ($B = 0.533, SE = 0.210, t = 2.54, p = .012$). None significant predictors were age, gender, and work hours (all $p > .05$). Higher educational attainment of family members is associated with a more positive television and film viewing culture, whereas other socio-demographic factors do not have a significant influence. With this, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected, and it is statistically established that socio-demographic characteristics, most especially education, significantly influence the television and film viewing culture (frequency and duration) among

families in Nigeria. Higher education is associated with higher TVC when only socio-demographic factors are considered.

Table 6. Regression of Household-Level Determinants on Family Television and film viewing culture (TVC)

Predictor	B	SE	t	p
(Intercept)	3.671	0.263	13.97	< .001
Family Size	-0.027	0.044	-0.61	.544
Family Role (Mother)	0.079	0.146	0.54	.589
Family Role (Child)	-0.226	0.180	-1.26	.211
Devices (DSTV / GOTV / StarTimes / Strong)	0.068	0.146	0.46	.645
Devices (Mobile Phone)	0.688	0.221	3.11	.002

Model Fit: F(5, 114) = 3.96, p = .002, R² = .148, Adjusted R² = .111

Table 6 highlights that the regression model which examines the household-level determinants of family television and film viewing culture (TVC) was statistically significant, $F(5, 114) = 3.96, p = .002$, explaining 14.8% of the variance in TVC ($R^2 = .148$). it reveals that availability of viewing devices significantly predicted positive TVC among families. Availability of mobile phones in families enhanced their TVC ($B = 0.688, SE = 0.221, t = 3.11, p = .002$). Other household-level determinants such as family size and family role were not significant predictors of TVC among families (all $p > .05$). therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that access to mobile phones which is an indicator of household-level factors significantly influence the television and film viewing culture of families in Nigeria.

Table 7. Unstandardised and Standardised Regression Coefficients for Socio-Demographic and Household-Level Determinants Predicting Family Television and film viewing culture (TVC)

Predictor	B	SE	t	p	β
(Intercept)	5.857	0.844	6.94	< .001	—
Gender (Female)	-0.515	0.293	-1.76	.082	-0.352
Age	-0.019	0.0069	-2.78	.006	-0.395
Education Level (Tertiary)	-1.155	0.584	-1.98	.051	-0.799
Education Level (Postgraduate)	-1.322	0.561	-2.36	.020	-0.917
Work Hours	-0.073	0.028	-2.66	.009	-0.276
Family Size	0.006	0.047	0.12	.904	0.012
Family Role (Mother)	0.513	0.297	1.73	.087	0.336
Family Role (Child)	-0.157	0.264	-0.59	.554	-0.094
Devices (DSTV / GOTV / StarTimes / Strong)	0.391	0.164	2.38	.019	0.267
Devices (Mobile Phone)	0.870	0.246	3.54	< .001	0.400

Model Fit: F(10, 109) = 4.07, p < .001, R² = .272, Adjusted R² = .205

Table 7 shows a series of regression conducted to examine the influence of socio-demographic and household-level determinants on family television and film viewing culture (TVC). Socio-demographic determinants alone significantly predicted TVC, $F(5, 387) = 3.64, p = .003, R^2 =$

.045. In this session of the model, education level was a significant predictor. Families with a member having tertiary education reported higher TVC scores ($B = 0.718$, $SE = 0.221$, $t = 3.25$, $p = .001$), and those with postgraduate education also had higher TVC scores ($B = 0.533$, $SE = 0.210$, $t = 2.54$, $p = .012$). Gender, age, and work hours did not significantly predict TVC (all $p > .05$). When household-level determinants were considered, the model also reached statistical significance, $F(5, 114) = 3.96$, $p = .002$, $R^2 = .148$. Access to devices was the strongest predictor: families with mobile phones reported significantly higher TVC ($B = 0.688$, $SE = 0.221$, $t = 3.11$, $p = .002$). Other household factors such as family size, family role, and access to DSTV/GOTV/StarTimes did not significantly influence TVC. This indicates that device availability plays a key role in shaping family viewing culture.

A combined model including both socio-demographic and household-level determinants was also significant, $F(10, 109) = 4.07$, $p < .001$, $R^2 = .272$, adjusted $R^2 = .205$. In this session of the model, older age ($B = -0.019$, $SE = 0.0069$, $t = -2.78$, $p = .006$) and longer work hours ($B = -0.073$, $SE = 0.028$, $t = -2.66$, $p = .009$) were associated with lower TVC, while device availability remained a strong positive predictor, particularly for mobile phones ($B = 0.870$, $SE = 0.246$, $t = 3.54$, $p < .001$) and DSTV/GOTV/StarTimes ($B = 0.391$, $SE = 0.164$, $t = 2.38$, $p = .019$). Conversely, when household factors were included, higher education levels which showed a positive significance alone, showed a negative association with TVC (tertiary: $B = -1.155$, $SE = 0.584$, $t = -1.98$, $p = .051$; postgraduate: $B = -1.322$, $SE = 0.561$, $t = -2.36$, $p = .020$). This indicates that when control indexes such as access to devices are introduced, higher-educated families may have slightly lower TVC. These standardised coefficients illustrate the relative importance of each predictor. While socio-demographic characteristics such as age and education have some impact on TVC, household-level determinants, particularly access to devices, exert the strongest positive influence on family television and film viewing culture.

Discussion

Family television viewing occurs at varying levels across households. Approximately 32% of respondents rarely watched television with their families, while 27.6% engaged in daily shared viewing and 20.4% watched together two to three times weekly. In terms of duration, most families typically watched television together for 1–2 hours per session (32.7%), with an additional 20.4% watching for 30 minutes to 1 hour. Television sets were the primary device used by 74.5% of participants, and Netflix was the most widely used platform at 29.6%. While shared family viewing is still practised among families in Nigeria, it is not a uniform experience across households. Some families maintain consistent co-viewing routines, whereas others experience reduced shared viewing due to differences in schedules, personal preferences, or access to multiple devices within the home. The predominance of one-to-two-hour viewing sessions reflects a moderate level of engagement that fits within typical leisure periods. The strong use of television sets shows that traditional viewing patterns remain relevant. Nonetheless, the popularity of streaming services corroborates the debates on the gradual shift towards digital and on-demand content.

Courtois and Nelissen's (2018) observation aligns with this study's finding that despite the rise of individualised media habits, family viewing persists as a meaningful activity. The pattern of irregular co-viewing also aligns with Kraus et al. (2020), who documented moderate reductions in shared television time but noted that the availability of multiple digital platforms still supports opportunities for co-viewing. Iheanacho et al. (2020) hints that although television remains a central leisure activity, not all content equally fosters family interaction, emphasising the role of

programme type in shaping shared viewing experiences. Similarly, Grant (2024) found that many families continue to engage in shared television experiences, reinforcing the idea that co-viewing maintains relational significance even in the digital media landscape. In line with the family systems theory, television viewing continues to function as an important interactional process within the family system. The persistence of shared viewing, even at moderate levels, supports the idea that families seek stability, cohesion, and connection through recurring shared activities. Television viewing thus remains a subsystem that contributes to communication, bonding, and the maintenance of relational balance within families.

Socio-demographic factors of family members significantly predicted family television and film viewing culture. Education level was the strongest predictor: families with tertiary-level education reported higher TVC ($B = 0.718$, $p = .001$), followed by those with postgraduate qualifications ($B = 0.533$, $p = .012$). Gender, age, and work hours were not significant predictors when considered independently (all $p > .05$). Overall, socio-demographic determinants explained 4.5% of the variance in family television and film viewing culture. Higher educational attainment among family members associated significantly with more frequent or structured shared viewing. Families with tertiary and postgraduate education may prioritise co-viewing as part of leisure routines, and they may have better access to information or resources that facilitate media engagement. Gender, age, and work hours had limited influence which indicates that, in isolation, these characteristics do not strongly determine shared television behaviours. The modest proportion of variance explained (4.5%) also suggests that socio-demographics alone do not fully capture the complexity of family viewing patterns.

Bassul et al. (2021) reported a similar finding that parents' sociodemographic characteristics, including education, influence children's television habits. Similarly, Grant (2024) highlighted that co-viewing enhances social interaction and family closeness, which may be more common in households with higher educational attainment. These findings are also consistent with Courtois and Nelissen (2018), who noted that while alternative viewing patterns exist, family routines are sustained when families actively organise shared media activities. Within the framework of Family Systems Theory, the significance of education suggests that it functions as a structural and resource-based factor supporting stable family interactions. It facilitates routines, communication, and coordination around shared viewing, that strengthens cohesion within the media subsystem of the family.

At the household-level, identified factors significantly influenced family television viewing culture. Access to mobile phones was the only significant positive predictor ($B = 0.688$, $p = .002$), while family size, family role, and access to DSTV/GOTV/StarTimes were not significant predictors (all $p > .05$). Household-level determinants explained 14.8% of the variance in television viewing culture. This highlights a stronger significant influence when compared with socio-demographic factors alone. The presence of mobile phones within a household facilitates shared television viewing, likely by enabling flexible, on-demand access to media. Family size and family role are insignificant predictors which indicates that structural characteristics of the household alone do not strongly shape viewing patterns. Instead, it is the availability of technology, particularly portable devices such as mobile phones, that determines whether families can consistently engage in shared media experiences. This reflecting the growing importance of digital access in shaping contemporary viewing habits.

Hänninen et al. (2021) and Olimma (2023), emphasised that mobile and digital devices enhance family communication and support flexible co-viewing arrangements. Inobemhe et al. (2025) similarly noted that households increasingly shift from traditional collective viewing to personalised viewing facilitated by portable devices. This demonstrates that the availability and mobility of devices are key enablers of shared media engagement, even when household structure or composition is less influential. In alignment with the perspective of family systems theory, device availability acts as a structural resource that supports family interaction within the media subsystem. Mobile phones help regulate participation and engagement across family members, preserving cohesion even when members are physically apart or have conflicting schedules. This illustrates how technology mediates interactional patterns, enabling families to maintain stability and connection in the digital era despite evolving routines and individualised media preferences.

Conclusion

Shared television and film watching culture is re-emerging as a socio-scholastic discourse concerned with how families negotiate leisure, communication, and cohesion in the digital era. In the context of rapid technological change, families are increasingly navigating between traditional television, streaming platforms, and mobile devices, making co-viewing both a cultural and relational phenomenon. In this study, we examined the frequency and duration of family viewing, the socio-demographic determinants, and household-level factors that shape television viewing culture in Nigerian households. Family co-viewing remains a relevant practice, with most households engaging in one to two hours of shared viewing per session, though frequency varied. Education level emerged as the strongest socio-demographic predictor, while household access to mobile phones was the most substantial driver of shared viewing. These results underscore that television and digital media remain important subsystems in families, supporting cohesion, communication, and intergenerational bonds even amid the individualisation of leisure. The study recommends that:

- i. Families should establish regular shared television or film viewing routines. They should plan out consistent sessions that fit within their schedules, to strengthen family cohesion and intergenerational bonding.
- ii. Households, especially those with members of different educational backgrounds, should actively involve all members in co-viewing activities, as higher educational attainment supports structured and meaningful engagement in family media experiences.
- iii. Families should ensure adequate access to multiple viewing devices, particularly mobile phones and tablets, to facilitate flexible and on-demand co-viewing, enabling shared media experiences even when members are in different spaces or have conflicting schedules.

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